

STRUCTURAL, MORPHOLOGICAL, ELECTRICAL AND DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES OF CR₂O₃ COMPOSITE POLYANILINE

Vaishali N. Birge¹, Manjunatha B², Nagajyoti³, Mahadeva⁴, Shruti Gogi⁵, Sangshetty Kalyane⁶

^{1, 4, 5 & 6} Department of Physics, Bheemanna Khandre Institute of Technology, Bhalki, Karnataka.
Email: sangshetty2016@gmail.com

²Department of Physics, Govt Women First Grade College, Jevergi Colony, Kalaburagi. Email: Manjunatha179@gmail.com

³Department of Physics, Government College (Autonomous), Kalaburagi-585105.

Corresponding author's email: Manjunatha179@gmail.com, sangshetty2016@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The polymerization of PANI/Cr₂O₃ was carried out with varying mass proportions using APS as the oxidizing agent. Analysis of these nanocomposites was conducted through physical methods, namely X-ray diffraction (XRD) and SEM, as well as AC, DC and dielectric measurements. XRD patterns revealed structural properties, while SEM micrographs exhibited agglomerations and highlighted the influence of different elements on the morphology of the composites, with typical grain sizes ranging from 10 to 20 nm.

Keywords – PANI, XRD, SEM, ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES.

Abbreviations

PANI -Polyaniline

APS- Ammonium persulphate

SEM -Scanning electron microscopy

XRD- X-Ray diffraction

FTIR- Fourier transmission

INTRODUCTION

The exploration of conducting polymer composites has garnered significant attention across diverse fields due to their wide-ranging applications [1]. PANI, an organic conducting polymer, exhibits both conductive and semi-conductive properties, achievable through electrochemical and chemical synthesis routes. PANI can be synthesized via various methods, each imparting distinct chemical and physical characteristics: leucoemeraldine appears in a fully reduced form, displaying a yellow hue, while protoemeraldine adopts a brown color. Emeraldine presents a green appearance, pernigraniline manifests as violet, and nigraniline appears blue [2]. Polyaniline stands out among conducting polymers, prized for its simple synthesis, remarkable electrochemical and optical properties. Its potential in gas sensing applications is particularly noteworthy, owing to its stable ecological footprint, controlled conductivities, and redox characteristics. Moreover, its

backbone offers numerous active sites facilitating gas analyte adsorption and desorption. However, challenges persist due to its poor solubility in organic solvents and relatively lower sensitivity compared to metal oxides. Combining polyaniline with metal oxides opens new avenues, enhancing polymer structure characterization and expanding its applicability in various fields, which has garnered significant interest among researchers [3-6]. Metal oxide spread polymers complex have together huge contract of attention starting researcher, since they frequently shows unforeseen cross possessions synergistically derives from both mechanism. One of the best samples for oxide materials is the Cr₂O₃ oxide; this is well known for valuable properties of oxide with important futuristic application [7]. The PANI/Cr₂O₃ nano-composite exhibits several advantageous properties, including non-toxicity, high hardness, superior purity, and a high melting point. Incorporating Cr₂O₃ oxide into the polymer offers additional benefits, particularly in enhancing doping applications for PANI. The high hardness and melting point of Cr₂O₃ oxides make them suitable for use as refractory agents. Nanostructured metal oxides show promise as materials for blending with polymer nanocomposites due to their mechanical, electrical, thermal, optical, and multifunctional properties. Polymer nanocomposites containing Cr₂O₃ oxides demonstrate favorable physical properties. [8]. The exploration of different materials has been significantly impacted by nanostructured metal oxides such as TiO₂, CuO, graphene, and functionalized graphene. Among these, Cr₂O₃ has garnered considerable attention in gas sensing applications due to its outstanding electrical, catalytic, and magnetic properties. Cr₂O₃ is recognized as a promising candidate for gas sensor design owing to its cost-effectiveness, high sensitivity, rapid response, and recovery rates [9-11]. In the present work, we report on a polyaniline doped with [PANI/Cr₂O₃] was synthesized using in-situ technique. The PANI delivers more energetic surface zone for the further indicator, Cr₂O₃ composites nucleate above polymer chains contributing to improved conductivity and stability of the nanocomposite material by interlinking the Pn polymer chains. The phase and morphology of all the synthesized samples were analyzed using basic characterization techniques such as XRD and SEM. The AC electrical conductivity of the samples was measured using the impedance technique within a frequency range of 10KHz to 1MHz at room temperature. Additionally, the dc electrical transport property of the composites was investigated within a temperature range of 40-180⁰C. It was observed that the incorporation of Cr₂O₃ oxide into the polyaniline matrix had an impact on the ac electrical properties of the samples.

Materials and Methods

All used chemically were investigative reagents (AR) grades. The monomeric aniline was twice as distil prior to use. ((NH₄)₂S₂O₈), Hydrochloric acid (H₂SO₄), Cr₂O₃ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Preparation of Cr₂O₃/PANI

At room temperature, a solution of 0.2M aniline was mixed with 1N HCl in a blender and stirred for 2 hours at a stable RPM. Subsequently, 0.2M ammonium persulfate was added to the blender. Cr₂O₃ nanoparticles were dissolved in the solution with continuous stirring for an additional 6 hours to ensure uniform suspension. After 6 hours, the resulting mixture was separated by filtration

and washed with acetone and deionized water. The resulting suspension was then incubated at 50°C for 24 hours. [12].

Flow chart of preparation of Cr₂O₃ Polyaniline

XRD of pure PANI and PANI/Cr₂O₃

The XRD instruments shows structural property of the samples when consider a pure PANI the figure shows the XRD pattern is broad peaks it means that pure PANI is amorphous nature The pure PANI peak in the range of 25°. The prominent peak is attributed to the periodicity in perpendicular and parallel directions of the polymer chains. The XRD results are consistent with the results obtained by other research groups. The average crystalline size of the PANI are estimated to be approximately 2.86 nm are calculated by using Debye -Scherer formula,

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$$

Where D is crystalline size, λ is wavelength, K is crystallite shape factor a good approximation is 0.9, β is FWHM and 2θ is angle (deg.) [13].

The XRD designs determine the compound are fine crystal-like and reveals that the peaks, which are fully equivalent to the works (JCPDS no. 751526). The PANI/Cr₂O₃ XRD peaks are shows

crystalline nature and the peaks are at angle of The average crystalline size of the PANI are estimated to be approximately 10-20 nm are calculated by using Debye -Scherer formula,

$$(D=K\lambda/(\beta \cos\theta))$$

Where D is crystalline size,

λ is wavelength,

K is crystallite shape factor a good approximation is 0.9,

β if FWHM and 2θ is angle (deg.)

FIG: XRD OF PANI and PANI/Cr₂O₃

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

The sem graph shows morphological structure properties the fig.1 shows it is spherically structural nature the Polyaniline elements with stretched chain form are detected. Meanwhile the HCL is used as protonic acid in the synthesis of PANI, the attendance of microcrystallinity form can be perceived. Since conducting polymers are very delicate to the heat, due to the contact between electron and the samples, substantial quantity of heat is produced which causes the growth of mall crackening in the sample through SEM record.

Figure shows SEM graph of PANI/CR₂O₃ composite.in this graph shows the particle is agglomerated, highly non porous granular size and strong interconnecting each other. Upon very high magnification, the observation reveals the presence of homogeneously distributed PANI/Cr₂O₃ within the polymer sample. The SEM study conducted on the samples shows numerous aggregated particles and pores, which have been minimized due to the homogeneous distribution of Cr₂O₃ in PANI. The presence of distinct Cr₂O₃ crystals significantly impacts electrical parameters such as conductivity and dielectric behavior of these composites. Image contrast arises from variations in scattering across different surface areas due to geometric disparities between Polyaniline and Cr₂O₃ [14-16]

FIG; SEM of PANI and PANI/Cr₂O₃

AC Electrical Conductivity

Polyaniline – Cr_2O_3 composites

This study investigates the frequency-dependent alternating current (AC) conductivity of polyaniline (PANI)– Cr_2O_3 composites with varying weight percentages (wt %) of Cr_2O_3 . The results reveal a consistent behavior of conductivity up to 10^5 Hz, followed by slight increases in conductivity for composites with higher PANI- Cr_2O_3 wt%. Notably, the conductivity of composites with 10 wt% PANI- Cr_2O_3 initially decreases after 10^4 Hz, then rises again. This anomalous behavior is attributed to the distribution variation of PANI- Cr_2O_3 within the composites. Specifically, at 5 wt% Cr_2O_3 -PANI, conductivity sharply increases due to the extended chain length of PANI, facilitating charge carrier polarization. Conversely, at 20 wt% Cr_2O_3 -PANI, conductivity decreases, likely due to charge carrier trapping. Subsequent conductivity increase is associated with altered Cr_2O_3 -PANI particle distribution, supporting enhanced charge carrier polarization between localized sites. [17-19].

FIG: AC conductivity of PANI and PANI/Cr₂O₃

DC conductivity:

The charge carrying apparatus in the pure PANI and PANI/ Cr₂O₃ composite, for the conductivity as function of temperature is studied. The dc conductivity increases exponentially with increase in temperature which is suggesting the behaviour of the semiconducting nature. The dc electrical conductivity also increasing as the content of Cr₂O₃ increased in the polyaniline matrix [20]

FIG: DC conductivity of PANI and PANI/ Cr_2O_3 **DIELECTRIC LOSS-; Polyaniline – Cr_2O_3 composites**

This study examines the dielectric loss behavior of polyaniline (PANI)– Cr_2O_3 composites across different weight percentages (wt %) of Cr_2O_3 . The dielectric loss, represented in Figure, exhibits a trend akin to pure polyaniline, showing an increase in $\tan\delta$ values with higher Cr_2O_3 -PANI content, while decreasing with increasing frequency. Remarkably, at frequencies beyond 1 MHz, these composites demonstrate nearly zero dielectric loss, indicating their lossless nature. This behavior aligns with the conductivity and dielectric constant results observed in these composites [21]. The momentary delay in the dielectric constant of a substance up on a change in the electric field due to characteristics phenomenon [22].

Fig shows the dielectric loss of polyaniline – Cr₂O₃ composite

CONCLUSION

The successful synthesis of polyaniline and PANI/Cr₂O₃ composite has been attained through chemical oxidation utilizing aniline hydrochloride as a monomer. XRD studies validate the formation of both PANI and its composite. The XRD pattern reveals that the PANI/Cr₂O₃ composite exhibits an orderly arrangement of the polymer chain, whereas the synthesized PANI displays a slightly crystalline nature. The increased conductivity was attributed to the formation of a better charge transport network in the relatively insulating PANI matrix. The investigation of PANI/ Cr₂O₃ Nano composites confirmed their stability and suitability for solar cells and optoelectronics devices. Dielectric characterization demonstrated that CR₂O₃ particles exhibit a strongly effecting in dielectric possessions of resultant PANI/ CR₂O₃ composites

REFERENCES

1. Arunkumar Lagashetty, M. Ameena, P. Anjalidevi, K. S. Darshan, K. Reshma, Shreeharsha, B. Manjunatha, Sangshetty Kalyani, V. Veena & Sangappa K. Ganiger , Interfacial synthesis, characterization and thermal studies of PANI/MAI₂O₄ (M= Mg, Zn) Nano composites, :Polymer Bulletin 2023/5/27, 1-17,(ISSN NO: **1700839**)
2. B. Manjunatha , Arjun N. Shetty S. Kaveri , Sundar S. Mety , K. C. Anjaneya , Ramakrishna Reddy, Sangshetty Kalyane Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, part of Springer Nature 2019 BioNanoScience ISSN 2191-1630 BioNanoSci. DOI 10.1007/s12668-019-00679-z Chemical Mediated Synthesis of Polyaniline/Tungstenoxide (PANI/CR₂O₃) Nanocomposites and Their Antibacterial Activity Against Clinical Pathogenic Bacteria.

3. E. M. Genies, P. Hany, and C. J. Santier, "A rechargeable battery of the type polyaniline/propylene carbonate-LiClO₄/Li-Al," *Journal of Applied Electrochemistry*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 751–756, 1988.
4. Y. Wang, H. Wei, J. Wang et al., "Electropolymerized polyaniline/manganese iron oxide hybrids with an enhanced color switching response and electrochemical energy storage," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, vol. 3, no. 41, pp. 20778–20790, 2015.
5. L. W. Shacklette, R. R. Chance, D. M. Ivory, G. G. Miller, and R. H. Baughman, "Electrical and optical properties of highly conducting charge-transfer complexes of poly(p-phenylene)," *Synthetic Metals*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 307–320, 1980.
6. B.-H. Kim, J.-H. Jung, S.-H. Hong et al., "Nanocomposite of polyaniline and Na⁺-montmorillonite clay," *Macromolecules*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 1419–1423, 2002.
7. Rahul Jabnoor¹, Manjunatha B², M V N Ambika Prasad³, Arunkumar Lagashetty⁴, and Vijaykumar Basavarajappa⁵, Sangshetty Kalyane⁶ Synthesis, characterisation and AC conductivity study of PANI/□-Fe₂O₃ nanocomposites IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 1221 (2022) 012001
8. B T Vijaykumar, B Bharati, K Priyanka, Ramabai, B Manjunatha and Basavaraja Sannakki Investigations on dislocation density and strain of polyaniline with CR₂O₃ nanocomposites IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 1221 (2022) 012017
9. N.R. Jana, Y.F. Chen, X.G. Peng, Size and shape controlled magnetic (Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni) oxide nanocrystals via a simple and general approach, *Chem. Mater.* 16 (20) (2004) 3931–3935, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/cm049221k>.
10. Dongzhi Zhang, Yingbo Jin, Yuhua Cao, Facile synthesis and ammonia gas sensing properties of NiO nanoparticles decorated MoS₂ nanosheets heterostructure, *J. Mater. Sci. Mater. Electron.* 30 (2019) 573–581, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10854-018-0323-3>.
11. G. Sarala Devi, V. Bala Subrahmanyam, S. C. Gadkari, S. K. Gupta, NH₃ gas sensing properties of nanocrystalline Cr₂O₃ based thick films, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 30, 2006, pp. 102–105
12. To investigate the crystalline grain size, morphological structure and microwave properties of PANI/PbO composite materials Nagajyoti, Manjunatha B, B T Vijaykumar, Arunkumar Lagashetty, Aparna Shetty, Sangshetty Kalayne research square DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2423049/v1>
13. Nagajyoti H, Anjaneya K C, Manjunatha B "Polyaniline (PANI): Preparation, Properties and Applications Microwave Absorbers" LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing (27 June 2023) ISBN-13 : 978-6206165828
14. Alan G. MacDiarmid Prof., "Synthetic Metals": A Novel Role for Org. Poly." The Nobel Foundation 2001, Volume-40, issue-14, *GDCh of page-2581*.
15. J.Stejskal et al., "Report on –Prep. of a conducting polymer", year 2002, 74(5), page number-857 of *Pure Applied Chemistry*, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1351/pac200274050857>
16. Manjunatha B, Mahantappa Limbitot, Manjula c Sangshetty Kalyane International Journal of Emerging Technology and innovative research (JEITR) entitled "Studies on structural,

surface morphology and transport properties of PANI-WO₃. 2018 JETIR September 2018, Volume 5, Issue 9 www.jetir.org (ISSN-2349-5162) <http://doi.org/10.1729/Journal.32712>

17. Sangshetty Kalyane, “ Synthesis, Characterization and ac conductivity Study of Polyaniline/ MgSnO₃ Composites”, International Journal of Materials Science ISSN 0973-4589 Volume 12, Number 2 (2017), pp. 175-180.

18. Chaturmukha V. S., Avinash B. S., Naveen C. S., Rajeeva M. P., Prasanna G. D., Harish B. M., Suresha S., Jayanna H. S., and Ashok R. Lamani, “Influence of compositional variation on electrical properties of PANI/SnO₂ nanocomposites, International Conference on Condensed Matter and Applied Physics (ICC 2015), AIP Conf. Proc. 1728, 020348-1–020348-4; doi: 10.1063/1.4946399, AIP Publishing. 978-0-7354-1375-7.

19. S. Manjunath, K. R. Anilkumar and M. V. N. Ambika Prasad, *Ferroelectrics*. Lett 366, 22–28 (2008)

20. R. H. Bughmass and L. W. Shacklette, *Phys. Rev. B*, 29, (1989), 5872

21. Sangshetty Kalyane, “ Synthesis, Characterization and ac conductivity Study of Polyaniline/ MgSnO₃ Composites”, International Journal of Materials Science ISSN 0973-4589 Volume 12, Number 2 (2017), pp. 175-180.

22. Manjunatha B, S.C.Gumma, Nagajyoti et al. 2022 Synthesis, Characterization and Enhanced Electrical Properties of Polyaniline-Tungsten Oxide Composites by in-situ Polymerization Technique, Research Square Version 2.